

Unbundled Smart meters in the new smart grid era

Assessment on compatibility with European standardisation efforts and with IoT features

Mihai Sanduleac¹

¹University Politehnica of Bucharest
Bucharest, Romania
m.sanduleac.ro@ieee.org

Abstract— With the new active distribution network where distributed energy resources are increasingly present and where Smart meters will become the most ubiquitous equipment in low voltage (LV) networks, the paper presents a new Smart Meter solution and a corresponding MV/LV dispatch center to contribute to both new energy market challenges as well as to Smart Grid services and evolving requirements. We are addressing some specific aspects of observability in LV network, based on wide-spread IP communication solutions, such as Synchro-SCADA and data anonymization, and presenting network services to assist dispatch, using also background network programs in LV such as power flow and state estimator.

Moreover, the paper is analyzing and proposing a unifying approach for both Smart Meters and Smart Grid architectures, to allow a complex Smart Grid functionality and with Internet of Things features. The concepts are in progress to be implemented in the European R&D project NOBEL GRID and developed also in the project Storage4Grid, showing the potential for generality.

Keywords—Unbundled Smart Meter, standardisation, SGAM, Internet of Things, Smart Meter eXtension

I. INTRODUCTION

Smart meters are the most ubiquitous equipment in a low voltage network. This is also the network level where most of the smart grid developments will have an important impact. Millions of Smart meters have been already deployed in LV networks, however most of them do not cover yet functionalities to really unleash the smart grid potential, neither the potential for new dynamic markets of energy and especially of energy services.

The Unbundled Smart Meter is proposing an architecture to cope with both metrology requirements, which make the measurements “legally enforced” (and thus can be used to invoice energy bills) and with the additional flexibility needed for smart grid and complex markets.

It is a common reality now that smart metering systems are envisioned for large deployments and that besides the billing functionality and complex tariffs, some functions to support the distribution system operator (DSO), such as improving maintenance and easier operation are becoming common features. In fact, the 2012/148/EU Recommendation, to support roll-out of smart metering in European Union [1], has 10 key common recommended functionalities, for the customer, for the meter operator – serving also the distributor

for network planning through enough frequent readings (e.g. each 15 minutes), for commercial aspects, for security and data protection and for the distributed generation - both-sides active and reactive energy metering (import/export), which is another feature to support the DSO.

But advancing towards Smart Grid is much more than that. It is about complex functionalities at each level, down to MV and LV networks, capable to support active network functionalities, to accept different levels of energy and energy services markets, including local markets within microgrids and islands, capable to support resilience and sustainability.

Smart Metering systems deployment, if well implemented, can bring substantial functionalities from the very beginning, which serve multiple stakeholders, add value – enabling new business models, and improve the return of investment, as the benefits are horizontal over many actors which can be involved.

The *Unbundled Smart Meter* (USM) approach [1] is a systematization where smart meter functionalities are adequately grouped into two separate (unbundled) components: one for metrological and hard real-time functions, called the *Smart Metrology Meter* (SMM), which is intelligent but has fixed functionality and high security of recorded data (black box-like standard, where data can be lost only after buffer recirculation after known periods, e.g. 3 months or one year) and a *Smart Meter eXtension* (SMX) which has high flexibility to accommodate new functionalities, to be deployed during the meter lifetime and to support the future evolution of the smart grid and energy services. The systematization is presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Unbundled Smart Meter architecture

With the re-design of Smart Meter within the USM architecture, it becomes a complex device that can cover

multiple purposes: a) Tariffication and billing, enhanced with complex load profiles required by deregulated markets; b) Real-time data for supporting SCADA / observability and network control functionalities in the active Low and Medium Voltage networks, dealing with increasing distributed production; c) Support for energy services, such as demand response or other services which may be aggregated and offered at higher levels, e.g. as ancillary services to the transmission system operator; d) support for power quality assessment, in order to match the delivered energy with the corresponding quality of service (QoS); e) Support for controlling production and storage units of the prosumers. For all these purposes, USM is designed to have advanced support for data security and for user privacy.

The group of functionalities b, d, e and the security requirement are also serving Smart Grid paradigm and open new opportunities for complex functionalities, while addressing also the concerns about security as killing factor for Smart Grid. The real-time data is already supported by some meters, through the so called “instrumentation values” [2], meaning real-time provision of measurements for u, i, p and q, but they are not usually used, even if their accuracy is in most cases higher than similar measurements obtained from classic SCADA measurements.

All these functionalities can be accessed directly from the same primary source – the meter, through a multi-user, multi-protocol solution, reachable over IP-based secured communication, using already existing infrastructures or deploying new one. The increased role expected to support Smart Grid is also enabled by the USM systematization:

a) The SMM part is relieved of complex communication tasks and allows better hard real-time functionalities. With this emphasis on real-time features, SMM supports now important new functionalities to better serve Smart Grid:

- increased dynamics in providing instrumentation values u, i, p, q, f, angles: from reporting rate of one up to five seconds in traditional meters, to 2 – 5 values per second for SMM, thus making it even a better measurement equipment than classic Remote Terminal Units (RTU) and Bay Control Units (BCU);

- More processed data available from the voltage and current waveforms: harmonics up to 25 – 32, in addition to THD (which is included in some traditional meters);

- a high number of different load-profiles, serving not only classic billing but also real-time records of rms values in event triggered buffers, with 2-10 Hz record resolution and 10 – 60 seconds of records and 1-2 seconds of pre-trigger memorization, thus bringing basic fault recording functions in each metering point;

- Distribution of probability - especially on voltage level, to support hourly based power quality through statistical means

b) The SMX part is released from metrology duties and from hard real-time tasks and is focusing on business logic and communication related functions, in a flexible framework:

- Network synchronization of SMX time with accuracy better than one second, to allow synchronous data acquisition

over the entire Smart Grid metering points [3].

- Support for distribution automation through Smart Grid agents deployed in SMX [4];

- Support for multi-user, multi-protocol approach for various actors needing direct data through end-point communication

- Support for agents allowing energy community empowerment through serious games hosted by SMX [5].

With all these functionalities, the USM becomes a key element acting as a gateway between the prosumer ecosystem and the actors which simultaneously interact with it, as depicted in figure 2.

Fig. 2: USM as gateway between prosumer and all external actors

II. EUROPEAN STANDARDISATION EFFORTS

The Unbundled Smart Meter is a new meter design which needs to be assessed in the frame of European standardization efforts. The multi-user concept of USM asks for multiple communication protocols, as each user may be from a different area of standardization. In addition to protocols, another issue is the fact that the data models associated to different area are not compatible as well. It is known for instance that COSEM and CIM data model are not yet unified, thus bringing space for hybrid data models. The approach is to keep meter-specific data model for the data in the USM, as being the main source of information compliant with latest OBIS codes / COSEM objects standardization from the official DLAM Association repository [6], and to map it to different data models and protocols (e.g. IEC 61850 or OpenADR), specific for each actor. The main standardization efforts which are assessed in this paper for compatibility are:

- Mandate M/441, which is a Standardisation Mandate to CEN, CENELEC and ETSI in the field of measuring instruments for the development of an open architecture for utility meters involving communication protocols enabling interoperability [7];

- Mandate M/490, regarding Smart Grids standardization [8]

The recommended communication architecture of a Smart Meter [9] has been released by CEN/CENELEC based on work enabled by [8], shows not only possible communication links, but also recommends specific protocols for each type of connection. Figure 3 presents this architecture (right side of the

picture) and shows the Smart Metering interaction with Smart Grid systems and with Home automation: left side of the picture, showing that even the systems are separate, they have common areas.

Fig.3: Reference architecture for metering and interaction with other systems

With the USM Smart Metering / Smart Grid simultaneous approach, the architecture from figure 3 need also to be harmonized with Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM), which defines in the Smart Grid Plane a specific dimension for the information management, considering different zones as hierarchical levels of the power system management [10].

III. COMPATIBILITY WITH MANDATE M/441

This mandate requested the standardization bodies to define interoperability and open architecture for utility meters. The most important document released by the CEN-CENELEC activity was “Functional reference architecture for communications in smart metering systems” [9].

This document gives a general architecture of the smart meter communication, as already shown in the right side of figure 3. The architecture allows different types of intercommunication between layers of functionality, for instance the “meter communication function” (MCF) of the metrology meter can connect with the Local Network access point (LNAP) – connection (link) M, with the Neighborhood Network Access Point (NNAP) – connection C and with the AMI (Automated Meter Infrastructure) Head-End system – through connection G1. This generality allows practically any approach, or a combination of them. To be noted that for cost-effectiveness, MCF is usually implemented in the microcontroller of the metrology part, thus being able to cover only a basic security layer, because its computational power is already highly used for real-time functions and for the implementation of the specific protocol for the allowed connections (M, C, G1).

The Unbundled Smart meter has systematized the functions and use only a part of the multiple possible combinations of communication architecture, as presented in the figure 4.

It can be observed that some of the connections from figure 3 are here in grey, showing that they are not used in USM communication. In the USM implementation shown in figure 4 there is no direct connection allowed from the “meter” with

metrology functions and the NNAP or with the AMI Head End system (links C and G1). This communication is possible only through LNAP, which also supports communication with the local display (link H1) and the home automation functions (link H2). With this approach, the security of local metering parts is enhanced, as the only access point is LNAP, which can be implemented by using a powerful equipment, to support complex security functions for all connections.

Fig. 4: Mapping USM on the Smart metering system architecture

The detailed implementation of the USM mapping on the smart metering communication is presented in figure 5.

Fig. 5: Detailed mapping USM on the Smart metering system architecture

In this figure the SMX part of USM takes the role of the Local Network Access Point (LNAP) of the Smart Metering Architecture, providing communication with NNAP and AMI headend, by using specific protocols such as DLMS/COSEM. The machine running the SMX is a powerful single board computer such as BeagleBone Black or Raspberry PI/3 running Linux operating system, which allows the implementation of a complex firewall which can manage

security and privacy aspects at a high level of expectancy. Moreover, many functionalities can run on the SMX platform, which includes agents for different actors and the control of home automation.

IV. COMPATIBILITY WITH MANDATE M/490

Mandate M/490 has been released in order to support European Smart Grid deployment. The activity under this mandate is complex and considers various aspects of the standardization. One important milestone was to release an European Smart Grid conceptual model [11]. The conceptual model is an extension of the NIS model, but includes two new domains comparing with the NIST vision, meaning the distributed energy resource (no. 8) and the flexibility entity (no. 9), as per figure 7.

Fig. 7: Smart Grid European conceptual model

SGAM Framework [10, 11] has been established to merge the concept of interoperability layers with a basic smart grid plane, within 3 dimensions: Domain, Interoperability and Zone.

Fig. 8: SGAM framework

In order to assess compatibility with SGAM, USM need to be mapped on SGAM layers as well. Figure 9 shows the position of USM on “Zones” axis.

On the Domains axis USM is mainly present in *Customer* or *DER* premises, including at the combination named prosumer and can be present in all interoperability layers. With this SGAM compatibility, an important aspect of compatibility was to find where can USM be placed in smart grids set of standards developed by CEN-CENELEC in [12].

Fig. 9: USM mapped on M441 and M/490 architectures

This document is looking for standardization aspects by using the approach based on most important high level use-cases (HLUCs). The authors selected some of most relevant HLUCs and projected the new USM device in some of them. Figure 10 shows USM projection in the SGAM component layer of the *Smart Metering systems* HLUC (8.5 in [12]), with the SMM covering MID meter in the *process zone* and the SMX covering LNAP and EMG (Energy Management Gateway) functions in the *field zone*. Merge of LNAP and EMG is a natural implementation of SMX, as this Linux part of the USM implements both communication with higher levels (here NNAP at *station level* and G3M at *operation level*) as well as functionality to run home applications such as EMG or demand response agents. To be noted that in [1], at the operational level is placed the DSO control platform named G3M.

8.5 Smart Metering systems

Fig. 10: USM projection on SGAM – case 8.5 from [12]

The same component layer addresses in [12] the *demand and production flexibility* (HLUC 8.6), where additional Smart appliance appears at the *field level*, while at *operational level* are proposed HES (Head End system) and FEP (Front-end processor) to acquire metering and demand response information and to provide data for MDM (Meter Data Management) and EDM (Energy Data Management). Figure 12 shows the mapping of USM (SMM+SMX) in this HLUC, which controls in [1] the smart appliance through a SHIC (Smart Home Intelligent Controller), while directly communication with HES (as billing system inside G3M in [1]) and FEP/EDM to provide aggregated flexibility service of many field-based SHICs and their white appliances.

Fig. 11: USM projection on SGAM – case 8.6 [12]

In order to be able to communicate with so many components (SHIC, CEM, HES and FEP), the multi-user, multi-protocol feature of the SMX inside USM was essential.

A third HLUC which is studied in terms of mapping on standardized HLUCs is the advanced distribution management system (ADMS, HLUC 8.3.3 in [12]). Figure 12 shows the mapping of USM on the component layer of this HLUC.

8.3.3 Advanced Distribution Management System (ADMS)

Fig. 12: USM projection on SGAM – case 8.3.3 [12]

This is an essential HLUC which traditionally is using in field and station level field devices and RTUs (Remote Terminal Units). Due to the special feature of USM as being able to provide real-time values to SCADA-DMS at operational level through a communication front end, the USM placed in such a HLUC is a novelty, showing that USM is enough flexible to cope with [12], even if at the date of releasing the document USM did not exist. The SGAM framework can be analyzed also for this HLUC at the level of communication layer. In figure 13 can be seen this layer having proposed by CEN-CENELEC the IEC 61850 protocol for the distribution domains, which is extended by using USM also at the DER and customer domains.

Fig. 13: USM projection on SGAM – case 8.3.3 on the communication layer

Moreover, the layer suggests that the IEC 61850 communication may need to be established even with more partners in the same time, in case that two different system, e.g. at station and operational level need data in the same time. Again, the USM architecture allows not only the IEC61850 implementation, but also simultaneous such connections in the same time. Our work in [1] had analyzed many other HLUCs of [12] and even valued new HLUCs which can be implemented with USM and in all of them it has been shown that there is compatibility of USM with today use-cases, without changing concepts, but adding value in domains related to end-users, including with emerging prosumers.

The CEN-CENELEC standardization in emerging smart grid is an important step towards high interoperability and holistic approaches. The showed in all studied cases, including in the ones presented in this paper, that USM is compatible with today and future developments, and that it is a valuable component serving a broad range of HLUCs at the level of DER and customer premises, as well at the distributed level, even if at this level traditional RTUs are also present. Figure 14 shows the Smart grid plane from [11] with the domains and zones axes, showing the area of deployed functionality by using USM.

The figure suggests that even the generation and transmission domains are eligible for the use of USM at least

as backup source of grid data, as the real-time measurements of smart meters are usually of high accuracy compared with traditional means (transducers, RTUs, BCUs). Moreover, through the complex combination of metering and real-time data support, the authors show that USM ensures a unification of essential smart metering and smart grid features, which is beneficial in terms of effort of implementing them.

Fig. 14: Smart Grid plane [11] and USM areas of application

V. USM AS AN IOT DEVICE

The USM architecture has the SMX as the intelligent and flexible upper part of the meter which is connected directly to public IP networks such as ubiquitous internet, which allows multi-user and multiprotocol implementations. In order to cover most of the actors interested in the USM data, four protocols have been chosen in USM: DLMS/COSEM for metering applications, IEC61850 for SCADA, OpenADR for demand response and MQTT for IoT purposes. The MQTT protocol is implemented with a strong Role based access control (RBAC) functionality, allowing communication with external actors based only on publish/subscribe topics approved by the local user, as legal owner of the USM data. By adding MQTT and JSON or JSON-LD messages exchanged with external actors through secure VPNs, USM enables applications easily developed by energy services companies, thus unleashing creativity and new businesses.

VI. USM - APPLICATION EXAMPLES

The USM architecture has the potential to implement various functionalities, which have been already verified by different business cases implemented without architectural changes in the projects Nobel Grid [1] and Storage4Grid [13]

In Nobel Grid USM provides several functions, and observability of the grid is one of the important functions in this project which is targeting to provide essential real-time data for the distribution system operator (DSO). Figure 15 presents the functional layer, showing the use of USM for network observability.

The figure shows that USMs are deployed in three domains of the smart grid plane: distribution grid (USM_G), DER (e.g. USM_{PV}) and customer premises (USM_C). While traditionally at distribution and DER domains it is used usually a remote terminal unit (RTU), and also at customer premises there is usually no real-time observability, the Nobel Grid solution uses the USM as a combined RTU and billing

data device at customer premises and at DER, while the distribution domain uses the same USM concept in important grid points, thus avoiding to add RTUs. The metrology part of USM is usually equal or more accurate than RTUs [2] in providing real-time measurements, because it uses for measurement specialized metering chips designed for precise measurement of energy, calculated from precise measurement of voltages, currents and powers.

Fig. 15: SGAM Function Layer for implemented grid observability for SCADA by using USM as process and field devices

In Storage4Grid project the USM allows the centralized control of distributed storage resources in a low voltage network by implementing a local storage-related agent which uses the energy data of the point of common coupling with the DSO, the local storage device data and centralized setpoints to optimize distributed storage use in power networks.

Figure 16 shows the functional layer for an advanced resilient prosumer, where its energy router controls local photovoltaic (PV) production, storage and resilient loads through a DC busbar [14].

Fig. 16: SGAM Function Layer for implemented an advanced resilient prosumer using local storage resources

The two components of USM₁, SMM and SMX are placed at customer premises in the Process and Field zones and the

SMX controls the SMX of a second level meter USM₂ which measures and controls a local charging point for electrical vehicles (EVs) and the energy router. The SMX of USM₁ is also communicating with a grid side energy storage system controller (shown as Grid ESS Control) and potentially with a SCADA system, which are both placed on the Operation zone. The grid ESS control can also interact with energy and energy services markets, placed in the market zone. Similar representations can be made for the component and communication layers, where the latest can show the used protocols for each use case.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The paper presents the Unbundled Smart Meter (USM) as enabler for multi-user, multi-domain purpose; the paper shows the important role of an advanced meter in supporting with high level functionalities and roles the evolving Smart Grid. As being a new architecture to be used in the energy field, also providing many functionalities embedded in the same equipment, it is presented an assessment regarding the compatibility with today efforts of CEN-CENELEC-ETSI on smart metering and smart grid systems. In this context, relevant documents based on M/441 and M/490 mandate are considered, and their architecture and high-level use cases are analyzed, by mapping the USM concept for relevant aspects of these standardization aspects, showing compatibility and enlarged potential of use in the Smart grid plane of SGAM. In this respect, even if the project [1] was focused mainly on the distribution, DER and customer domains, it is suggested that the transmission and generation domains can take advantage of the high precision of the measurements and of the high flexibility in terms of connection to various SGAM zones.

One conclusion is that the approach allows a natural unification of Smart Metering and Smart Grid architecture, strengthening the role of Smart Meters in the Smart Grid new era and allowing more dynamic developments towards a comprehensive development of the smart grid paradigm while also advancing towards IoT connectivity through MQTT or other related technologies. Examples of using the architecture to implement different functionalities in two European projects (Nobel Grid and Storage4Grid) are also presented, by mapping the functionalities in the functional layer of SGAM.

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